

An Experimental Platform of a Beyond-5G Network with Machine Learning Integration

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Abstract—As commercial 5G networks become commercially available and 6G looms in the horizon, the adoption of these new technologies depends on the way current and yet-to-come vertical industries put them to use. This accelerates the process of adoption by the end users, which are the final consumers of these technologies. 5G networks have multiple use cases associated with its new features, being the Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC) use case one of the most instrumental for verticals such as remote teleoperation, factory automation and autonomous driving. In this paper, we design a general purpose and low-cost end-to-end (E2E) 5G/Beyond-5G Experimental Platform for URLLC applications, supporting Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS) with Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) capabilities for online data analytics and automated decision making. The experimental evaluation of our platform demonstrates an average one-way latency on the DL and UL as low as 4.1 ms and 6.60 ms, respectively, 13.8 ms of end-to-end latency (E2EL), and a 31.7 ms E2EL between UEs for data frames of a teleoperation Web App with video feedback, demonstrating the capability of our platform in relation to other state-of-the-art testbeds for URLLC applications.

Index Terms—5G, Beyond-5G, 6G, URLLC, PaaS, AI/ML

I. INTRODUCTION

The introduction of 5G, specified by 3GPP [1], has a huge disruptive potential not only across the communication's industry, but also in user-level application markets and the manufacturing of gadgets and appliances i.e. the framework of Internet of Things. This disruption is due to the technologies introduced by 5G [2]: increased carrier bandwidths allowing up to 20Gbps data rates per User Equipment (UE) [3], network softwarization achieved through Network Slicing (NS), ultra low latencies and Multi-Edge Computing (MEC) support.

NS builds on Network Function Virtualization (NFV) [5] and Software-Defined Networks (SDN) technologies. NFV leverages virtualization to decouple network functions from hardware encapsulating them in Virtual Network Functions (VNFs), or in containers as Cloud-Native Network Functions (CNFs). Likewise, SDN decouples the network control and forwarding functions, allowing for programmable network control and abstracting the infrastructure from applications and network services. By leveraging NFV and SDN, NS enables the creation of virtual networks i.e. network slices, in which every slice has an owner, or tenant, that rents physical resources from the Infrastructure Provider (InP). Beyond

network slicing, NFV-based systems can provide Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS) capabilities, allowing tenants to deploy customized slice management elements, and also to provide applications in the Cloud, with many deployments done in conjunction with fog and edge computing [6].

Orchestrating and managing a large number of network slices and their traffic volumes requires state-of-the-art automated mechanisms that need to be adaptable, agile and feasible to deploy. Data-driven approaches based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) have proven viable in this context to provide the level of adaptability and automation beyond previously known heuristics, resulting in the integration of AI/ML-based solutions for system and service data analytics, and for orchestration and management resulting in the Beyond-5G (B5G) communications paradigm. Following this trend, the next generation of technology, namely 6G, is expected to take AI/ML integration further by redesigning the network with AI as a native architectural feature [7].

These new technologies have created new vertical industries with new services that can be categorized in three 5G use-cases: 1) Ultra Reliable Low-Latency Communications (URLLC) 2) enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), and 3) massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC). In this work, we propose an End-to-End (E2E) B5G Experimental Platform for URLLC applications, such as Factory Automation (FA), Autonomous Driving (AD) and teleoperation [8]. Different URLLC applications have different latency requirements: FA requires less than 1 ms end-to-end latency (E2EL, one-way latency for data transmission), while E2EL for AD is between 10 and 100 ms [33]. Our platform achieves a competitive E2EL of 13.8 ms for a teleoperation URLLC use-case supporting PaaS in an infrastructure based on the ETSI Open Source Management and Orchestration (OSM) framework with AI/ML integration, following the trend towards Native AI for 6G [7].

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section II provides context regarding the contribution of 5G platforms and related work. Section III provides insight on the hardware components of our platform, while Section IV focuses on the software for AI/ML and PaaS support. Section V explains the URLLC use-case deployed, and Section VI provides a numerical evaluation for it. Section VII presents conclusions and future work.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Several testbeds have been developed at different scales to adjust the operations of a 5G/B5G system to the end user's preferences and demands. Although various 5G platforms are proposed in the literature, many of them do not address the integration of AI/ML, such as those presented in [9]–[11]. Vidal et al. designed a multi-site testbed for Small Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (SUAVs) that provides a dynamic configuration in NFV and MANO for smart farming. A distributed testbed for 5G networks is presented by Chamran et al. [10], in which the Device-to-Device (D2D) communications are supported and evaluated, reporting a 24.1-105.6 ms end-to-end delay. In addition, the proposed work by Völk et al. integrates 5G networks and satellite communication maintaining compatibility with 3GPP Release 15. A more comprehensive study of 5G network deployments is presented in [12], where the SA mode outperforms NSA mode, especially regarding latency (4-10 ms one-way DL latency) and packet loss.

In contrast to the aforementioned studies, the authors in [13] developed an integration of AI applications to their proposed testbed which measures an application-based E2E delay of 15.8-131.1 ms, but limiting slicing at the RAN domain and VNFs application-oriented replacement. One of the first True-data Testbeds for 5G/B5G Intelligent Networks (TTIN) in SA mode is presented in [14], providing data collection (14 ms E2E delay) and an AI engine with 3GPP standard compatibility. Nevertheless, the parameter configuration in TTIN is fixed and predefined, which may not support optimal network management. One of the most recent testbeds, so-called GAIA 5G [15], provides virtualization in three domains (i.e., Fog, Edge, and Cloud), allowing vertical services to be implemented. However, the authors declare that the presented testbed may not be successful in large scenario deployments and requires further development towards B5G technologies.

According to the existing literature on 5G testbeds using *ping* [16]–[18], E2EL can be varied from 4-70 ms, which causes higher values for Round Trip Time (RTT) latency. However, our platform measures E2EL on the UL and DL using more reliable procedures, yielding more reliable measurements. The experimental platform in this paper addresses is unique in the sense that it addresses a B5G URLLC teleoperation use-case with AI/ML integration for optimal management and orchestrations leveraging PaaS features

III. E2E B5G EXPERIMENTAL PLATFORM WITH AI/ML INTEGRATION

The E2E B5G Experimental Platform presented in this paper is a general purpose 5G cellular network embedded with different AI/ML approaches for network analytics, orchestration and automated management for 5G/B5G use cases. Its design is presented in Fig. 1, showing the 5G Core (5GC) Cloud Domain and the Radio Access Network (RAN) Domain with MECs.

A. 5G Core Cloud Hardware of the E2E B5G Platform

To support the software stack (5G Mobile Core, Cloud Computing support, Orchestration frameworks, etc.) of our platform, two clustered servers with high-performance computing capabilities are deployed, which conform the 5GC Cloud. The Operating System (OS) running in both servers is Ubuntu 20.04 with LXD 5.1 [20], which is a next generation system container and virtual machine manager (VMM).

The first server (S1) has an Intel Xeon Gold processor, with 26/52 cores running at 2.10GHz with 192GB of RAM memory and an ASUS ATX motherboard. While the second server (S2) has an Intel I9-10900L processor with 10/20 processor cores. The storage devices in S1 are: 1) one SATA SSD with 2TB of storage, and 2) a NVMe SSD disk with also 2TB of storage. The former is used to host the Ubuntu 20.04 filesystem and user-level data in two separate partitions. The latter is managed by *zfs* [21], and it is used by LXD as an storage pool to allocate storage for all the VMs and containers that the server handles. S2, on the other hand, only has one NVMe SSD.

Both S1 and S2 have 10Gbit Ethernet interfaces connected with each other through a Layer 3 Netgear switch with 10 Gbit interfaces as well. This switch allows the creation of VLANs amongst VMs/containers across the servers, and even supports virtual routers, allowing flexible network design across the VMs/containers. S1 is also provisioned with an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 GPU (available to VMs through GPU Passthrough [22]) used for training AI/ML models for KPI prediction and automated orchestration/management with relatively large datasets using CUDA and/or Python/Tensorflow.

B. 5G Mobile Core

The 5G Mobile Core is an instance Open5GS [23], a C-language Open Source implementation of a 5G Mobile Core and Enhanced Packet Core (EPC), i.e. the core network of the New Radio for 5G and the Long Term Evolution (LTE) network. Our deployment of Open5G works in Stand-Alone (SA) mode, supporting only 5G network functions (NFs).

The VM in which the 5GC is running is provisioned with 8G of memory with 4 processor cores with Ubuntu 20.04 as the OS with Docker and Kubernetes (K8s) [24] for container and orchestration support. Alongside with this, the 5GC also integrate data collection and visualization capabilities using Grafana and multiple components of its software stack for real-time examination of the NFs of Open5GS. Grafana Loki is used to ingest the logs generated by the VNFs of Open5GS, and Grafana Promtail is used to parse them and process them for display. Moreover, Grafana is able to connect to different database engines, in particular InfluxDB, to present real time information of different KPIs gathered.

C. MEC Capabilities

Open5GS allows a flexible deployment of its NFs across different VMs and different network nodes. In order to exploit the modular features of the 5GS in our deployment, a containerized version of Open5GS using Docker/K8s is necessary. Containerization of the Open5GS software stack enables the

Fig. 1: End-to-End Beyond-5G Experimental Platform with AI/ML Integration and PaaS Support.

online migration and caching of the NFs across servers and containers/VMs, materializing MEC capabilities. Specialized networking configurations are necessary for seamless online NF migration, and these are supported by SDN and virtualization capabilities at the network level.

D. Features at the RAN Domain

At the RAN domain, the E2E B5G Platform consists of two Amarisoft gNBs supporting up to 500 UEs, allowing for configurable QoS flows. Both of this gNBs only support SA connectivity to Open5GS, and each has one cell with a MIMO 2x2 configuration. It also comes integrated with a proprietary 5GCore, which has been used for the prototypes of other use cases [25]. The gNB enables the configuration of PHY and MAC layer RAN parameters, such as the number of channels available for Uplink (UL) and Downlink (DL), the number of DL/UL slots, DL/UL symbols, Hybrid Automatic Repeat request (HARQ) parameters, among others, that significantly affect the speed and quality of the gNB's transmission.

E. UE Devices

The UEs currently configured in our testbed are: 1) two OnePlus 8T 5G phones, 2) a Raspberry Pi 3 with a 5G modem attached as a HAT (Hardware Attached on Top), 3) a Teltonika TRB500 5G gateway. The 5G HAT is a SIM8200EA-M2, based on the Qualcomm snapdragon X55 platform, providing data rates up to 2.4 Gbps on the DL and 500 Mbps on the UL. Moreover, it can also work as a 5G Wireless Router providing Wifi hotspots for 5G-enabled devices to easily access the 5G network. The Teltonika TRB500 comes with an integrated Ethernet interface allowing devices on the Ethernet LAN to connect to the 5G mobile network transparently.

IV. ORCHESTRATION, MANAGEMENT AND AI/ML INTEGRATION

The appropriate software stack is necessary to exploit the capabilities of our 5G network infrastructure in order to integrate AI/ML algorithms, support PaaS, and achieve the low-latencies required by URLLC applications. AI/ML algorithms are data-driven, so it is necessary to deploy data monitoring mechanisms with appropriate data stores in order to build reliable models for analytics and orchestration.

A. Monitoring

Given the distributed, cloud-native and PaaS-oriented design of our E2E B5G Experimental Platform, it is necessary to deploy suited monitoring mechanisms. To achieve this, we have deployed a distributed Monitoring System (MS) [26] that leverages cross-domain PaaS resources in order to sample system metrics in close proximity to the sources of measurements.

The cloud-native design of the MS leverages the virtualization capabilities of our B5G platform, relying on Docker/K8s for the deployment and orchestration of measurements VNFs. The MS provides a REST API for its online reconfiguration, which includes the measurement VNFs, the frequency of measurements and Lifecycle Management Operations related to sampling loop orchestration. The MS is also able to sample metrics from VMMs, Virtual Infrastructure Managers (VIMs) and Container Infrastructure Managers (CIMs), all of which are a critical part of Management and Orchestration (MANO) frameworks necessary for PaaS support.

The MS provides a data store based on InfluxDB [27] for storing data on a time series basis. This provides the raw data that can be used for predictive analysis, fault detection, classification and clustering, or different forms of data-driven techniques of analysis which are instrumental for orchestration and management mechanisms.

B. AI/ML-Based Analytics for Metrics and KPIs

Our E2E B5G Experimental Platform has deployed multiple instances of an AI/ML-based context-aware predictor that can be used to forecast KPIs at any level of granularity given the provision of time series data. This predictor is based on Context-Aware Traffic Predictor (CATP) [28] originally developed for traffic prediction of base stations. Given its design, it can provide KPI prediction not just in the RAN Domain, but also at the 5GC Cloud, at the MEC, or even transport when present.

CATP is a state-of-the-art time-series predictor that embeds system-level knowledge regarding resource orchestration and management into its training model. Thus, it yields prediction better tuned for use by management and orchestration algorithms. Its instances have been re-factored for a cloud-native environment, and they query data from the MS through

a Kafka interface [29]. However, the predictor instances should remain close to the compute resources in order to maintain the training process time- and energy-efficient.

Predictors and other analytics engine can also be federated, allowing them to remain as close as possible to the data sources and the data stores provided by the MS. This reduces the overhead in bandwidth consumption associated to large data transmissions, instead transmitting the model parameters of the predictors.

C. PaaS for Management and Orchestration

Our E2E B5G Experimental Platform provides PaaS using a hybrid orchestration approach in which a K8s Container Infrastructure Service Manager, alongside a conventional OpenStack Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM), shares resources under a common ETSI-compliant NFV orchestrator (NFVO) [4], namely Open Source MANO (OSM), which is in charge of the network resource orchestration. OSM will create, orchestrate and delete VMs that will host the K8s clusters, while K8s works as an orchestrator for the applications. Thus, K8s will be deployed as an overlay network, while the underlay network is conformed by Openstack (the VIM) and OSM. In this setting, our platform allows for network functions to be deployed as VNFs or CNFs alike. Fig. 2 shows how K8s is supported via OSM, in which the K8s nodes form a cluster with a single master node.

The primary aim of the OSM MANO is to coordinate and orchestrate NFV Infrastructure (NFVI) resources and map them efficiently to various VNFs, interconnecting them realizing more complex network services. OSM supports Virtual Network Function Descriptors (VNFDs) and Network Service Descriptors (NSDs), in which VNFDs define needed VNF resources in terms of compute resources and logical network connection points, while NSDs manage the connection point links using virtual links among the interconnected VNFs, mapping them to the physical networks provided by the VIM.

OpenStack provides a series of core services to provision VMs of resources and interconnectivity as well. Moreover, it also provides a centralized service for authentication and authorization of OpenStack services, connectivity between these services, persistent block storage volumes, resource

Fig. 2: PaaS Support in the E2E B5G Experimental Platform.

provisioning for VMs, cloud resource telemetry and automatic creation of resource stacks. K8s, as the system overlay and the Container Infrastructure Service Manager, provides the means to support container-based deployment within PaaS clouds, focusing specifically on cluster-based systems. Generally speaking, K8s works as the main platform for managing containerized workloads and services that facilitates both declarative configuration and automation.

D. Intelligent Orchestration and Management

Designing mechanisms for orchestration and management is one of the central issues in B5G and 6G communications due to, among other things, the sheer amount of traffic that they are expected to support, the decentralized nature of the architectures and the services they run. Following and extending an approach similar to [30], our E2E B5G Experimental Platform has been designed to deploy Reinforcement Learning (RL) mechanisms in conjunction with AI/ML-based data analytics leveraging the underlying PaaS capabilities to automate orchestration and management of traffic flows to optimize different system KPIs. An architectural diagram of an integrated deployment for AI/ML-based automation can be seen in Fig. 3, which shows the deployment of the MS with CATP and two RL algorithms: one for admission control of User Service Requests (USRs) and SCHE2MA [31] for VNF placement and migration.

Given the cloud-native design of our E2E B5G Experimental Platform, the RL algorithms are containerized and deployed close to the points of actuation. The communication between the MS, CATP and the RL algorithms happens through a Kafka publisher/subscriber (PUB/SUB) interface, which allows the MS to store data in a general Database Management System (DBMS) in the 5GC Cloud. Notice that SCHE2MA does not rely on any form of KPI analytics.

V. DESCRIPTION OF THE URLLC APPLICATION

The URLLC application consists of a Web-based front-end in which a user issues commands to a remote mobile robot through our E2E B5G Experimental Platform.

A. Web Server and App for the URLLC Application

An HTTP Web server (WS) was developed using Flask in Python3.8 which runs in the controller of the robot. The WS

Fig. 3: Platform integration of AI/ML algorithms.

(a) Web App on a Web Browser. (b) Gazebo for Robot Emulation.

Fig. 4: Visuals of Use Case Deployment.

receives commands from the client, usually another 5G UE, running the browser-based Web App. The browser interface is developed with HTML, CSS and Javascript. Fig. 4a shows the Web App in an OnePlus 8T 5G phone. When a user issues a command through the controller pad of the Web App, it triggers an AJAX POST request to the WS which forwards the commands to the robot through a Robot Operating System (ROS) [32] interface running on a separate thread (ROS thread). ROS provides a PUB/SUB interface that allows low-level device control and robot messaging.

The WS runs another thread, the telemetry thread, with the purpose of reading the robot status every 0.25 s i.e. telemetry data, consisting on position, speed and orientation. The telemetry thread reads this information from a Redis data store in which the ROS thread writes the information coming from the robot. The telemetry thread, upon reading the data from the Redis store, displays data dynamically on the Web App through a WebSocket interface implemented with Turbo-Flask, while the video feedback is streamed into the Web app.

B. Mobile Robot Environment

By using ROS, the software stack of the Web App becomes agnostic to the specifics of the mobile robot. Thus, any ROS-compliant robot can be easily interfaced with the WS. For prototyping purposes, the mobile robot has been simulated using Gazebo, a well-designed simulator to rapidly test algorithms, design robots and train AI models using realistic scenarios for robots of different morphologies and properties. Fig. 4b shows the Gazebo environment for the simulated mobile robot, which provides telemetry data with high-accuracy and video feedback since it can simulate cameras of varying resolution. All sensors and cameras in Gazebo have corresponding ROS-compliant publishers, facilitating interface with external software.

VI. EVALUATION OF THE E2E B5G PLATFORM FOR URLLC APPLICATIONS

We evaluate the average E2EL in Fig. 5 between the Rpi3+HAT and different destination nodes. To measure one-way latency (OWL) and two-way latency (TWL), we used the One-Way Active Measurement Protocol (OWAMP) [34], and the Two-Way Active Measurement Protocol (TWAMP) [35], respectively, and *ping* for RTT latency. Only *ping* was used

Fig. 5: Latencies from the RPi3+HAT towards different nodes.

Fig. 6: 5G phone latencies towards different nodes.

when performing measurements to the Internet (8.8.8.8), since there are no public servers for OWAMP/TWAMP.

Fig. 5 shows that the OWL of the UL by the RPi3+HAT towards the 5GC incurs a 6.6 ms latency, while the TWL and *ping* report 9.20 and 10.40 ms, respectively. Measuring the OWL from the 5GC to the RPi3+HAT i.e. OWL of the DL, resulted in 4.1 ms, 37.9% slower than the DL transmission. Measuring E2EL towards the Robot (Teltonika/TRB500) results in 13.8 ms, double the latency towards the 5GC. A separate one-way DL measurement from the 5GC to the Robot resulted in 6.6 ms, showing consistency with the measured E2EL value. The TWL from RPi3+HAT to the Robot and *ping* are 25.00 and 24.71 ms, respectively, showing consistency with the UL and DL latencies. Measuring latency towards the Internet and the 5GC yielded 21.37 and 10.40 ms (smaller than the E2EL towards the Robot). In this case, UL transmission only occurs at the RPi3+HAT, not at the destination. However, all latencies are below **30 ms** for all cases.

Fig. 6 shows 5G phone latencies which are higher than those of the RPi3+HAT because the configuration of the gNB used for the RPi3+HAT and the Robot enables faster data transmission through the RAN, resulting in symmetrical ULs and DLs. This configuration, however, is not compatible with the OnePlus 8T 5G phones, for which a different configuration was used in which the DL has more throughput. Thus, *ping* to the Internet and the 5GC Cloud are of similar values, while it is much slower to the Robot (UL transmission in both directions).

Fig. 7 shows the throughput measured using *iperf* [36] at the RPi3+HAT and the 5G phone. As expected, the UL and DL of the RPi3+HAT have similar throughputs due to the gNB configuration, shown in Fig. 7a. A different outcome is observed for the OnePlus 8T in Fig. 7b, since the UL and DL throughputs are not symmetrical when measuring throughput towards the Internet and the 5GC. The exception is the case for the Robot, which shows a symmetrical throughput because of the UL utilization upon transmission on both sides.

Finally, we measured the Control Loop Latency (CLL) of the URLLC Web App running in the OnePlus 8T 5G phone. CLL is the time between a command transmission

(a) Throughput of the RPi3+HAT. (b) Throughput of 5G Phone.
 Fig. 7: Network performance of RPi3+HAT and the 5G phone.

and the reception of the acknowledgement from the server. The average CLL is **63.3 ms**, yielding values around **31.7 ms** for E2EL of data frames from the 5G phone to the mobile robot assuming transmission throughputs shown in Fig. 7b. These latencies demonstrate the capability of our E2E B5G Experimental Platform for URLLC applications with video feedback in relation to other testbeds for similar use cases.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented an E2E B5G Experimental Platform with PaaS support and a high degree of AI/ML integration for KPI analytics, management and orchestration. It is able to fulfill latency requirements for a range of URLLC applications, demonstrated for our teleoperation Web App, keeping E2EL to a maximum of 31.7 ms. For future work, we will reduce E2EL further increasing the applicability of our platform, scale up the URLLC-related load and evaluate our AI/ML capabilities on different experimental scenarios.

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